

Renyi Entropy, Additivity and Maxwell-Boltzmann Free Energy

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In (1), Shannon's entropy, $S = - \sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$ is described as an average of the information function $\ln(f_i)$ and it is suggested that one may create different averages of information and hence different entropy functions. (1) suggests that one consider Renyi entropy in this light and further notes that it is additive like Shannon's entropy for $P_{new} = \sum_{i,j} p_1(i) p_2(j)$. (1) also argues that if one uses the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) probabilities in the Renyi entropy expression: $\ln\{\sum_i f_i^q\} / (1-q)$, then one obtains an expression in terms of MB free energies $F(T)$ and $F(T/q)$.

Here, we try to consider Shannon's entropy in terms of two body elastic scattering with time reversal balance. In such a case, additivity first arises due to conservation of energy, e_1 and e_2 , as the \ln function converts $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ into a sum. Even in the case of Tsallis entropy, one may introduce a function $\ln(G)$ which has additive properties. {The entropy then is $\sum_i P(f_i) \ln(G(f_i))$ which is not additive.} Given the Shannon MB case, the presence of \ln means that the term: $\ln\{\sum_i f_i\} = \ln(Z(T))$ appears naturally as the \ln of the normalization constant. Furthermore, given: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, multiplying both sides by q yields: $\ln\{f_i^q\} = -e_i q/T$. Thus, the Shannon MB case is already linked with a power law probability found in the Renyi entropy expression. In other words, the additive form of the defined Renyi entropy is in a sense the \ln of a normalization constant of an MB distribution with f_i^q , $f_i = \exp(-e_i/T)$, with f_i^q as a new set of unnormalized probabilities. This, we argue, shows the origin of the expression, given in (1), of Renyi entropy using MB probabilities leading to a function of $F(T)$ and $F(T/q)$ where F is the Shannon-MB free energy, i.e. $-kT \ln(Z)$.

Two Body Scattering

It is known that Shannon's entropy $- \sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$ is additive for $\sum_{i,j} f_i f_j \ln(f_i f_j)$ due to the behaviour of the \ln function. This may be seen another way by noting that:

F (free energy) = $E(\text{average}) - TS$ ((1)) for Shannon's MB entropy

In this case, $F = -kT \ln(Z)$ where $Z = \sum_i f_i$ where $f_i = \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((2a))

Then, $E_1 \text{ ave} + E_2 \text{ ave} - T(S_1 + S_2) = -kT(\ln(Z_1 Z_2))$ ((2b)) where $Z = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$.

In other words, the form $\sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$ appears naturally, but this is simply the normalization function for $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

The function $\exp(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained by maximizing the function $\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!)$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f_i$ if one uses Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$. Alternatively, in order to see how the additive feature of \ln appears, one may consider two body time reversal balanced elastic scattering:

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((3a)) $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((3b))

Taking \ln of ((3b)) in order to make it appear as a sum and equating with ((3a)), multiplied by a constant yields;

$$\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{where } f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ i.e an unnormalized probability ((4))}$$

One may multiply ((4)) by a constant q leading to:

$$\ln(f(e_i) \text{ power } q) = -e_i / (T/q) \quad ((5))$$

In other words, two body scattering associates a different temperature T/q with a new set of unnormalized probabilities, i.e. the product probability $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$. This leads to the normalization factor:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \text{ power } q \quad ((6)) \text{ instead of the usual } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i = Z \quad ((7))$$

We thus argue that the ingredients of Renyi entropy are already present in the Shannon MB case if one considers two body scattering. In other words, Renyi entropy seems to be linked with the \ln of a normalization constant of a set of unnormalized probabilities $p_i \text{ power } q$ even if $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i = 1$. We suggest that this accounts for the free energy related results of (1).

Renyi Entropy

By examining two body Shannon-MB elastic scattering, one may consider the math function, namely the \ln of the normalization of $f_i \text{ power } q$:

$$\ln(\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \text{ power } q) \quad ((8))$$

As shown in the above section $f_i \text{ power } q$ represent a new set of MB probabilities linked with T/q , so ((8)) which is the definition of Renyi entropy when divided by $1-q$, is really $\ln Z(q/T)$ if one uses MB unnormalized probabilities $f_i = \exp(-e_i/T)$. This explains the origins, we argue, of the result of (1):

$$S_{\text{Renyi}} = 1/(1-q) \ln(Z(T/q)/ Z(T) \text{ power } q) = - \{F(T/q) - F(T)\} / (T/q - T) \quad ((9))$$

We note that Renyi entropy is additive just as $\ln(Z1) + \ln(Z2) = \ln(Z1Z2)$ as shown in ((2b)).

Here $F(T)$ is the Shannon-MB free energy. Thus, instead of simply linking Renyi entropy to Shannon's by using $q \rightarrow 1$, if MB probabilities are used, then Renyi entropy is \ln of the normalization of a set of MB probabilities as the $f_i \text{ power } q$ is linked with T/q .

Conclusion

In (1), a connection between Renyi entropy and Shannon Maxwell-Boltzmann probabilities is given. We argue that this connection may be seen if one derives the MB distribution using two body time reversal balanced scattering because: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where $f(e_i)$ is the unnormalized probability $\exp(-e_i/T)$. The probability normalization constant is then $\ln(Z(T)) = \ln\{\sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)\}$. Multiplying both sides by a number q associates a new set of unnormalized probabilities f_i power q with a new temperature T/q . Thus, the Renyi entropy $= \ln\{\sum_i f_i \text{ power } q\} / (1-q)$ is directly linked to the T/q MB case if MB probabilities are used in the Renyi expression. This then shows the origins of the expression ((9)) in (1) by viewing two body elastic scattering with time reversal balance.

References

1. Ozawa, M. and Javerzat, N. Perspectives on Physical Interpretations of Renyi Entropy in Statistical Mechanics (2024) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2404.06436v1>